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Articulation of Civil Engineering Ethics. What is the specific purpose of the profession?

E. Giménez-Carbó

Associate professor

Universitat Politècnica de València

Valencia, Spain

esgimen@cst.upv.es

ABSTRACT

This paper justifies the need for the articulation of civil engineering ethics. The professionals can adapt this ethic, to allow them to guide their work towards achieving the internal goods in their profession.

The text establishes the importance of the civil engineering and reviews the role of professional associations as custodians of “*good and correct work*” of its members both technically and ethically. The paper argues the reasons why codes of conduct, ethical codes or deontology are insufficient.

The article suggests the necessary steps to achieve a consensus on the universal ethics of civil engineering, in the current context of engineering practice in a globalized world. The text remarks the need to initiate a dialogue involving the maximum participation of all the civil engineering areas, with professionals and external agents to define the ethical code of the profession, understanding the ethical code as a conduct to which civil engineering achieves its meaning and social legitimacy.

This will be the beginning of the articulation of ethics of the civil engineering world.

Conference Key Areas: Ethics in Engineering Education, Engineering Skills, Curriculum Development.

Keywords: Civil Engineering Ethics, Professional Responsibility, Internal Goods.

INTRODUCTION

Civil Engineering responds to the needs of society and nature and, based on theories and tools of science and technology, creates products and gives benefits to the society. The current world, in crisis, needs practical solutions and needs engineering to solve current problems, such as the generation of renewable energy, access to potable water, waste water treatment and pollution control, the improvement of global communications and transport systems, achieving the millennium goals for

sustainable development, mitigating the effects of greenhouse gases or adapting to climate change [1], [2].

To be able to face these challenges, the engineers receive training during their studies at the University. And then, day by day in the course of their professional life, must complete and expand. This causes competent professionals with solid technical knowledge that allows them to find (technical) solution for any problems that is outlined. But engineering often lacks humanistic training that allows them to contextualize the projects that they develop, or raise questions about the effect of their work on future generations.

In the following section, the author points the corruption problem in Spain and how to stop it. Then she suggests the model of the Professor A. Cortina to be applied to the civil engineering ethics and finally ends with the conclusions.

1 PROBLEMS ABOUT CIVIL ENGINEERING IN SPAIN

1.1 The spread of corruption virus and how to stop it

Either by the training or the evolution of modern society, in recent times (at least in Spain) the profession of civil engineering has been linked in too many cases of corruption. Corruption can range from diverting funds to enrich some professional personally, to the construction of unnecessary infrastructures that the State finances with public money. All too often we read headlines in the press where the engineers seem to feel no responsibility for their projects.

Various codes of ethics/codes of conduct have been developed to try to establish the proper behaviour of these professionals [3], [4], but corruption cases surrounding civil engineering are still very frequent. John Ladd has argued against the uncritical acceptance of codes of ethics as authoritative ethical guides [5]. His main point is that ethical principles cannot be established by organizations or their members. On the other hand, only those belonging to a particular profession, know the purpose and the means they have to do a certain job (they are custodians of the body of knowledge of that profession), and on this is based the claim that professions must be autonomous, must be self-governing [6]. If the members of the profession do not regularly comply with their obligations, it should be the society that demands greater regulation in the profession.

For this reason, in this text, a model of ethics is provided that will predictably contribute to improve the training of these professionals and to guide their work to achieve the internal good of their profession.

Therefore, we believe it is fully justified the need to incorporate the teaching of ethics to civil engineering students, as a way to provide them with the necessary tools to act as correctly as possible, taking into account all aspects presents and futures that will affect their decision making.

In our view, it would be a mistake to introduce subjects of ethics in the curriculum that will treat the subject in a general way, without differentiating the context in which the studies are conducted and with a few variations on the content received by secondary students. It would be more about articulating an applied ethics and, from that, to study real cases and to arrive at a conscious decision making and argued on the way to act.

In order to arrive at that moment, the first step will be to articulate a civil engineering ethics. It would be advisable for the professionals to know this ethic in the moment of

exercising their profession. And we think that the model of applied ethics proposed by Professor A. Cortina [7] would be applicable.

2 THE PROPOSAL

According to Professor Cortina, to design the applied ethics of civil engineering would be necessary to follow the following steps.

2.1 Determine the specific purpose, the civil engineering internal good, by which civil engineering acquires its sense and social legitimacy.

It is essential that future civil engineering professionals know the internal good of their profession. Let us remember that the internal good of practice is what gives sense and legitimacy to a profession, in the words of Professor A. Cortina [7]. We have to define what the internal goods of the civil engineering profession will be, and for this we must not forget that the practice of engineering seeks the welfare of the people and communities in which they live.

Many of the internal goods of this activity will be associated with technical excellence and could be among others; the imaginative and practical use of science and mathematics, deep knowledge of the subjects necessary to develop the activity and in short would be to have the necessary training to develop the activity in an excellent way. Other internal goods would be related to safety, social and environmental sustainability of the projects planned, and to the profitability of the projects. It would try to give the best possible service to society.

If we want to go a little further in the definition, we could also consider the promotion of human rights and the search for peace as internal goods to the civil engineering profession. And for many engineers the greatest internal good will be the satisfaction of contributing to the flowering of people through the pursuit of technical excellence.

In any case, a debate is needed between civil engineering professionals to define the internal goods of the profession, since although they can be intuited, there is still no consensus about them.

As external goods, professor Cortina [7] mentions money, prestige and power. And as it says, we have to work to obtain internal goods and with this we will get external goods, but these should never be the end of our work.

Engineer Meredith Thring [8], one of the pioneers in thinking about engineering ethics, said: "*The subjective qualities of human life, such as personal fulfilment, happiness, freedom and love, are much more important in the long term for people affected by a (for their) engineering work, than the possession of goods and status symbols beyond those necessary for a full life.*"

2.2 Find out what is the appropriate means to produce the internal goods in a modern society.

Of course the right way to produce the internal good in civil engineering practice is to perform this practice in an excellent way, taking into account all the actors affected by the intervention, and studying the short and long term effects of the intervention in the environment.

The only way to ensure that it is done properly is to continually review the training that students receive in engineering schools and examine professional practice. In addition, in engineering schools, students should be encouraged to work as a team and with professionals who are not civil engineers. Only then they will be prepared to

form multidisciplinary teams, which are likely to be the ones that obtain the internal goods of the civil engineering profession.

In our opinion, ethics committees (so-called in the case of Spanish Association of Civil Engineers), the Professional Conduct Committees (in the case of the ASCE (American Society of Civil Engineers)) or similar, should be empowered, exercising in a serious and rigorous way their role. In order to do this, it will be necessary to address all complaints of professional malpractice, studying each case and sanctioning if it is concluded that there is a bad practice. This, in addition to giving visibility and importance to the ethical behaviour of the profession, will be used to rearrange and revise the existing codes, in addition to ensuring compliance. It will be a way of granting social legitimacy to the profession.

The search for the external goods of the profession cannot be allowed to be accepted and encouraged socially.

In most cases, major civil engineering works contain a large number of technical, social and environmental aspects that interact with each other and sometimes change the environment in an irreversible way. So it will be necessary to create ethics committees that study all the variables affected by the action. These ethics committees will be multidisciplinary and through dialogue and being aware of the responsibility for the execution of civil works, will ultimately decide the need for the action.

2.3 To inquire what virtues and values need to be incorporated to achieve the internal good of the profession.

MacIntyre's definition of virtue in *After Virtue* is: "*A virtue is an acquired human quality that enables us to acquire the internal good to a practice and the absence of which prevents us from achieving such goods*" [9].

This definition establishes a causal relationship between the exercise and possession of virtues, and the achievement of internal goods by practice. For MacIntyre among the desirable virtues (it would be advisable that the civil engineer also possessed them) would be justice, truth and courage. We can also identify certain desirable and appropriate human qualities in engineering practice. The Royal Academy of Engineering of Great Britain has identified four elements as "fundamental principles" that should guide engineers in achieving professional excellence: "*Accuracy and rigor; Honesty and integrity; Respect for life, law and the public good; Responsible leadership, listening and informing*" [10].

These principles can be applied at any time in the work of the engineer, but some of them are particularly relevant in different aspects of their work. Thus, *accuracy and rigor* are especially relevant to the technical aspects of their work; application of mathematics, physics, scientific knowledge and practical knowledge. We would be highlighting professional technical competence. The requirement of *honesty and integrity* will be especially relevant when negotiating the commission of a particular project. We must keep in mind that current engineering is an international activity and acceptable business standards can vary greatly between different cultures. For this reason it is necessary that the civil engineers be honest and complete and only accept those projects that are able to perform for an adequate cost.

Respect for life, law and the public good is an essential recognition taking into account the deep effects that engineering can have on the flourishing of the individuals and communities in which they live. The proper expression of this respect

requires us to be very careful, because the effects of the engineering activities can have a very large impact on the territory and time.

For all this, and because of the confidence that the citizens have in their engineers, which arises from their training and acquired knowledge, it is necessary that they take the reins and behave as *responsible leaders*, who listen and inform all the actors involved in a given project. Engineers possess the knowledge and skills that enable them to solve problems and realize opportunities, and also have the ability to identify these problems and opportunities.

2.4 To discover what are the values of the civil moral of the society in which it is inscribed and what rights does that society recognize to people.

For Professor A. Cortina, civil ethics is the set of values that citizens of a pluralistic society already share, whatever their conceptions of good life. The fact that they already share the values, allows them to build their lives together [11]. In this set of values should be equality, freedom, solidarity, active respect and attitude to dialogue.

When performing an engineering work such as the construction of a dam, we are obliged to respect the rights of all agents involved in the intervention. We will have to study if it is morally acceptable for society to destroy the environment in which the dam is to be located.

As Adela Cortina says "*in order to obtain social legitimacy an activity must, at the same time, produce the goods expected of it and respect the rights recognized by that society and the values that such society already shares*" [12].

In the current scenario where the work of an engineer can be done in any country of the world, it is the professional's obligation to study and to know the cosmovision of the territory in which a project will be carried out, to know the values of civic morality and the rights that society recognizes for people.

2.5 To ascertain what values of justice demand the principle of the discourse ethics, related to a universal critical moral, which allows us to put in question existing standards.

Normally in most western countries the existing standards protect citizens and all are treated as equal before the law. But in the current scenario of the practice of civil engineering in the globalized world, where it is usual to develop the activity in developing countries and in societies where existing morale is unacceptable under the magnifying glass of the inhabitants of the first world, It is necessary to establish a universal critical morality that, from the moral criteria of justice, may call under consideration and condemn existing norms [13].

The scope of a critical moral is broader than positive law. Therefore, engineering companies or engineers who work in companies with laws that do not adequately protect their citizens, must comply with current legislation, but do not settle to it, but must resort to the principles of a critical moral.

Therefore, when the civil engineer must intervene in the territory, in order to make fair decisions, they will have to (in the words of A. Cortina) "*attend to the prevailing law, to the prevailing moral convictions, but also to find out what values and rights be rationally respected*" [14].

The procedure that we consider valid to ascertain which norms are morally correct will be the discursive ethics of K.O. Apel and J. Habermas. The most important feature of this procedure will be that we will not have a rule like correct, if the rule has

not decided by everyone affected by it, after a dialogue held in conditions of symmetry.

2.6 Leave the decision-making to the citizens concerned, with the help of advisory instruments, they will weigh the consequences using criteria drawn from different ethical traditions.

This last step would derive directly from the previous one. In order to make any decision to intervene in the territory, it will be necessary for all those affected to intervene in conditions of symmetry, providing each of the persons involved with the same importance.

All those affected will have all the information available, much of it provided by the technicians who, in an honest and truthful manner, will explain the scope and consequences of the action. A dialogue will be established in which different criteria can be interpolated from different ethical traditions, contextualized for the moment and the specific area in which we find ourselves (hermeneutical way). Since, as Professor Cortina says, "*a single model of ethics is powerless to guide the decisions of the political and economic worlds, medical, ecological or simply, civic coexistence*" [12].

Therefore, we are forced to take into account the different models at the right time, although the coordinating element will be the discourse ethics, because it has its roots in communicative action and subsequent argumentation, which constitute the means of coordination, although not the substance of other human activities [12], [15].

3 CONCLUSION

It is very difficult to apply the scientific method and draw conclusions from a paper like the one presented here. This is because many dimensions of human life do not need a method to be understood, and this can be applied to the field of ethics. It is possible to say that in this field the important thing is the arguments more than the method. Despite these limitations we dare to conclude:

The model of applied ethics, proposed by Professor Adela Cortina, is applicable and can serve as a frame of reference in the ethical training of civil engineering professionals.

Being a good professional, a good engineer, implies an excellent behaviour not only in the workplace, but also requires similar behaviour in the social field. The ethical obligations, to be useful, must cover all activities and all the members of society. It is very important to provide individuals with sufficient training and experience to understand the importance of making ethical decisions. And allow them to develop their work being aware of the responsibility acquired and the consequences of their works.

The concept of responsibility that is handled in the field of civil engineering is insufficient. The meaning of the term should be broadened and legal responsibility should not be mentioned as the only obligation to be fulfilled by civil engineers.

We think that critical hermeneutics with a dialogical character and under the protection of the ethics of responsibility, is a good a method of articulating an ethics of civil engineering.

To do this, one of the first steps will be open a dialogue at the international level, to define the internal goods of the profession. This dialogue which should have the

maximum representation of all actors related to the practice of civil engineering, with all professionals and all people Involved.

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